

PROCESSING AND DURABILITY COMPARISON OF A POLYURETHANE THERMOSET AND A HOT-MELT THERMOPLASTIC ADHESIVE SYSTEM BONDED TO GALVANIZED STEEL

Chongchen Xu¹, Jonathan Verhoff¹ and Karthik Ramani¹,

¹ *School of Mechanical Engineering
Purdue University
West Lafayette, IN 47907-1288, USA*

SUMMARY:

A new thermoplastic bonding process, whose total cycle is less than 120 seconds, has been developed for galvanized steel (GS) to glass fiber reinforced polypropylene (GFRPP). The durability and failure modes of this thermoplastic adhesive bonded system, GS/HDPE (high density polyethylene based adhesive)/GFRPP, were compared to a thermoset adhesive bonded system, which is a GS/MCU (moisture cure urethane adhesive)/FRP (fiber reinforced polyester composite), after cataplasma and cyclic moisture aging. The solvent wipe bonded joints for both systems show the same durability in cataplasma environment, but in cyclic moisture aging the thermoplastic system retained a higher percentage of its strength than the thermoset system. The thermoset system adhesively failed at galvanized steel/adhesive both before and after aging, however the thermoplastic system failed adhesively at the PP composite/adhesive interface before aging and was partially cohesive failure after aging. Both the thermoplastic system coated with a primer on galvanized steel surface and the thermoset system treated with cleaner show reduced moisture durability compared to untreated samples.

KEYWORDS: adhesive bonding, durability, fiber reinforced, moisture cure urethane, modified high density polyethylene (HDPE), galvanized steel, single lap shear.

INTRODUCTION

Adhesives are widely used to bond dissimilar materials. Thermoset adhesive systems are often used to bond galvanized steel to thermoset composites. On the other hand, thermoplastic bonding of galvanized steel to thermoplastic composites has not been well developed. We first develop a new bonding process for galvanized steel to polypropylene composite using a thermoplastic adhesive. Then, we compare the durability and failure modes of a thermoset system with the thermoplastic system. In this study, a moisture cure urethane was used to bond polyester composites to galvanized steel and a new thermoplastic adhesive was used to bond polypropylene (PP) composites to galvanized steel. This study relates the long-term environmental durability of these two systems. Shear strengths, failure modes, moisture permeabilities and processing are discussed.

SAMPLE MATERIALS AND PROCESSING

ASTM 5868 single lap shear samples were used to study the effects of moisture on galvanized steel bonded to a composite for both of the adhesive systems. These lap shear joints have a 25.4 mm overlap, and all samples were cut to 25.4 mm wide from larger bonded samples. Figure 1 shows the single lap shear joint and its dimensions.

Fig. 1: Single lap shear joint

Thermoset System

The adherends were 1.27 mm thick hot-dip galvanized steel (GS) and 1.91 mm thick random fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester (FRP). Both GS and FRP were wiped clean with acetone and isopropyl, respectively, before any surface treatment. The adhesive used was a moisture cure urethane (MCU) with a bondline thickness of 0.76 mm. All GS/MCU/FRP joints cured at room conditions for two weeks before being placed in the aging environments.

For the cyclic moisture aging experiments, three surface preparations were employed. The three surface preparations were a cleaner (isopropyl alcohol, alkyl titanate), a metal forming lubricant (water-soluble organic soap, diethanolamine) used when forming sheets of galvanized steel, and as wiped clean with acetone and isopropyl. The cleaner was used on both GS and FRP and allowed to dry for 15 minutes before bonding. In previous testing, it has been shown that the organic soap increases lap shear strength for galvanized steel. The organic soap was only applied to the galvanized steel surface and was allowed to dry for 30 minutes before bonding.

Thermoplastic System

The thermoplastic system used primed and unprimed galvanized steel (GS) adherends. The unprimed galvanized steel adherend was 1.27 mm thick hot-dip galvanized steel, and the primed galvanized steel was 0.53 mm thick hot-dip galvanized steel with a polyester melamine based primer. The composite was a unidirectional glass fiber reinforced polypropylene (GFRPP) with a thickness of 2.20 mm. GFRPP was bonded to GS using a 76 μm thick modified high-density polyethylene (HDPE) based adhesive. The effects of heating time, heating temperature and pressure on the lap shear strength of bonded joints were

studied to determine a process window. Processing temperature did significantly affect the bonded lap shear strength (see Figure 2) while heating time and temperature remained 30 seconds and 176 °C respectively. The temperature in the range of 170°C~190 °C gave higher and repeatable joint strength. Both processing temperature and time may affect the repeatability of joint strength. Prolonged heating time and high processing pressure damage the GFRPP/HDPE interface due to the squeeze-out of adhesive and polymer. A typical thermoplastic processing cycle used for GS/HDPE/GFRPP bonding is shown in Figure 5 with a total cycle time less than 120 seconds.

Fig. 2 Effect of temperature on shear strength of GS/HDPE/GFRPP joints

Fig. 3 Effect of pressure on shear strength of GS/HDPE/GFRPP joints

Fig. 4 Effect of temperature on shear strength of GS/HDPE/GFRPP joints

Fig. 5 Optimized bonding cycle for GS/HDPE/GFRPP system

EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

Cataplasma Aging

Cataplasma aging was employed to accelerate the degradation of the adhesive joint by moisture and temperature. The cataplasma test submitted lap shear samples to 70 °C soak environment. To achieve this environment the samples were wrapped individually in cotton soaked with deionized water. The cotton and samples were placed in sealable polyethylene bags. The bags were placed on a stand in a 5 gallon container. The 5 gallon container has 2 inches of deionized water in the bottom and the container was sealed with a lid. The container is placed in an oven at 70 °C. Cataplasma aging was done for a period of 5 weeks.

Before the cataplasma samples are tested, the samples were removed and allowed to dry at room conditions (23 °C and 35% relative humidity) for 72 hours. This cool down and dry out period is necessary since the presence of excess moisture and elevated temperatures greatly effects the test results of adhesive joints.

Cyclic Moisture Aging

Cyclic moisture aging was done by hanging the lap shear samples in the environmental conditions listed in Table 1. The complete cycle takes 1 week, and the cycle was repeated for 5 weeks.

Table 1: The aging cycle for the cyclic moisture test

Time (days)	Relative Humidity (%)	Temperature (°C)
5	100	50
1	50	22
1	--	-22

RESULTS

Aging by cataplasma caused severe corrosion of the galvanized steel adherends, while cyclic moisture caused less severe corrosion of the adherends. This may be due to the lack of oxygen, carbon dioxide and the constant soak environment in the cataplasma aging that is not part of the cyclic moisture aging. According to Bremont [1], rapid corrosion can take place in the constant soak environment due to the inability of the zinc layer to form a protective zinc carbonate layer.

Moisture Cure Urethane

The urethane bonded system dropped in strength from 0.91 to 0.70 MPa (23% drop) after cataplasma aging (see Figure 6). Failure mode for the urethane bonded system was adhesive at the galvanized steel interface before and after cataplasma aging (see Figures 8 and 9). After cataplasma aging the galvanized steel interface had white corrosion around the edges and dark corrosion in the center of the joint.

Fig. 6: Cataplasma aging

Fig. 7: Cyclic moisture aging

Cyclic moisture aging caused lap shear strengths to drop from 1.09 to 0.79 MPa (28% drop) for the solvent wiped samples. This drop in strength is statistically no different from the drop in strength for the cataplasma aged samples (see Figures 6 and 7).

The cyclic moisture aging caused a drop from 1.26 to 1.09 MPa (14% drop) for samples that had the organic soap wipe on the galvanized steel adherend (see Figure 7). Initially samples with organic soap wipe had some partial cohesive failure, but after cyclic aging adhesive failure at the galvanized steel adhesive interface increased from 60% to 75% of the failure area.

Fig. 8: Solvent wipe control sample

Fig. 9: Solvent wipe cataplasma sample

The cleaner that was applied to the galvanized steel and composite surfaces caused failures to be completely cohesive and lap shear strengths to increase from 1.09 to 1.96 MPa. After cyclic aging the failure mode was cohesive/adhesive very near the composite interface (see Figure 11). Lap shear strengths dropped from 1.96 to 1.33 MPa (32% drop), and the standard deviation increased significantly (from 0.15 to 0.40 MPa, Figure 7).

Fig. 10: Cleaner control sample

Fig. 11: Cleaner cyclic moisture sample

The cleaner appears to have a detrimental effect on the ability of the composite adhesive interface to resist moisture attack. Typically the bond between the composite and moisture cure urethane adhesive does well in a cyclic moisture environment. In contrast the cleaner applied to the galvanized steel surface improves overall lap shear strength and resistance to moisture degradation of the interface between the galvanized steel and the adhesive.

HDPE Based Tie Layer

For the solvent wipe only sample, the strength of the lap shear joints dropped from 7.26 to 5.63 MPa (23% drop) after cataplasma (see Figure 12). The joints were initially adhesive failure at the polypropylene composite interface (see Figure 14(a)). Glass fiber could be seen on the fracture surfaces. After aging, the edges of the samples failed cohesively while the central part of the samples still failed adhesively at the PP composite interface (see Figure 15(a)). The thermoplastic adhesive material on the fracture surface of the galvanized steel was in many places thin enough to see through. Looking through the thin layer of thermoplastic material it could be seen that the galvanized steel surface had some dark corrosion.

For the galvanized steel with primer, the strength of the lap shear joints dramatically dropped from 8.48 to 0.97 MPa (89% drop) after cataplasma aging (see Figure 12). Initially the joints failed primarily adhesively at the PP composite interface (see Figure 14(a)). After cataplasma aging, the joint failures changed to primarily adhesive failure at the interface

between the galvanized steel and the primer (see Figure 15(b)). The primer shows a detrimental effect on the durability of the joints in the cataplasma environment.

Fig. 12: Cataplasma aging

Fig. 13: Cyclic moisture aging

(a) Solvent wipe without a primer

(a) Solvent wipe without a primer

(b) Solvent wipe with a primer

(b) Solvent wipe with a primer

Fig. 14: Control sample

Fig. 15: Cataplasma sample

(a) Solvent wipe without a primer

(b) Solvent wipe with a primer

Fig. 16 Cyclic moisture sample

Both primed and unprimed joints retained about 95% of their initial strength after cyclic moisture aging as shown in Figure 13. Failure for both the unprimed and primed samples was still adhesive at the PP composite interface for most part of the fracture surface as shown in Figure 16. Primer has little effect on the durability of GS/HDPE/GFRPP joints in this cyclic moisture environment.

DISCUSSION

It is interesting to note that the solvent wipe urethane bonded joints and the unprimed HDPE joints both had about 23% drop in single lap shear strength after cataplasma aging. After cyclic aging the solvent wipe urethane bonded joints had statistically the same percent drop (28%) in lap shear strength as for cataplasma aging. However, the unprimed HDPE joints showed a statistically smaller drop (about 5%) in lap shear strength after cyclic aging. This appears to be due to the moisture absorbing capabilities of the separate systems in combination with the relative concentration of the moisture environment. Weight gain samples of the PP composite (0.03% gain) and the polyester composite (0.73% gain) show that the polyester composite absorbs moisture more readily than the PP composite (data taken in a 50 °C, 90% R.H. environment after 5 days).

In both the urethane system and the HDPE systems it was seen that the incorrect application of a surface preparation method that is meant to increase joint strength can have overall detrimental effects on durability. In the urethane system the application of the cleaner to the composite adherend reduced the moisture durability of that interface, and in the HDPE system the primer on the galvanized steel surface significantly lowered the durability of the galvanized steel interface in the cataplasma environment.

Another interesting comparison is that the dark corrosion products of galvanized steel can be seen on both the HDPE and the urethane samples after cataplasma aging even though only the urethane samples does the corrosion seem to dominate joint strength.

Table 2: Percent drop in single lap shear strength

Adhesive	Surface prep.	Cataplasma aging	Cyclic moisture aging
Urethane	solvent wipe	23 %	28 %
	organic soap	N/A	14 %
	cleaner	N/A	32 %
HDPE	unprimed	23 %	5 %
	primed	89 %	3 %

CONCLUSIONS

The lap shear strength of the HDPE bonded system, 8.4 MPa, was an order of magnitude higher than those of the moisture cure urethane bonded system, 0.91 MPa. Cataplasma aging caused significant corrosion to the galvanized steel, while cyclic aging was less corrosive to the surface of the galvanized steel.

For the solvent wipe and unprimed samples, the percent drop in lap shear strength after five weeks of cataplasma was equivalent, 23% drop for each. Moisture penetrated to the galvanized steel adhesive interface for both systems in cataplasma aging as seen by the dark corrosion of the zinc layer. Even though moisture penetrated the galvanized steel interface of

both systems in cataplasma, the HDPE bonded system had partially cohesive failure while the urethane bonded system was dominated by interfacial failure at the galvanized steel interface. Cyclic moisture aging of the same systems showed the same drop in strength for the urethane system (28% drop), while the HDPE system showed a significantly smaller drop (5% drop). It appears that the moisture absorbing properties of the adherends in combination with the moisture environment are responsible for this difference.

Both the primer for the HDPE adhesive and the cleaner for the urethane adhesive can be detrimental to durability. The primer for the HDPE system used for our study did poorly in cataplasma aging due to interfacial attack at galvanized steel/primer interface. The cleaner applied to the polyester composite caused that interface to be weakened by cyclic moisture aging, this same cleaner which is primarily isopropyl greatly improved the strength of the galvanized steel interface. Our studies demonstrate that all aspects of any adhesive system, adhesive, primer and environments, must be carefully considered before put into use in manufacturing.

REFERENCES

1. Bremont, M. and Brockmann, W., "Improvement of the Durability of Zinc-Coated Steel/Epoxy Bonded Joints", *Journal of Adhesion*, Vol. 41, 1994, pp. 147-168.